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TECHNICAL REPORT OF GOLDFISH BREEDING

R.M.P.P Bandula

**Undergraduate
(BBST of
Agricultural
Technology)**

**University of
Colombo**

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Introduction

Scientific classification

Kingdom: *Animalia*

Phylum: *Chordata*

Class: *Actinopterygii*

Order: *Cypriniformes*

Family: *Cyprinidae*

Subfamily: *Cyprininae*

Genus: *Carassius*

Species: *C. auratus*

Binomial name: *Carassius auratus*

The goldfish (*Carassius auratus*) is one of the most popular and beloved freshwater fish species in the world. Known for its striking appearance, vibrant colors, and ease of care, goldfish have been kept as pets and ornamental fish for centuries. In this introduction, we'll explore some key aspects of goldfish, including their history, characteristics, care requirements, and significance in various cultures.

In the wild, goldfish are native to East Asia, but they have been introduced to many other parts of the world due to their popularity as pets. They thrive in ponds, lakes, and slow-moving waters, feeding on plants, small insects, and crustaceans.

Originating from the ancient waters of East Asia, particularly China, goldfish have a rich history dating back over a thousand years. It is believed that they were first domesticated from the wild crucian carp (*Carassius carassius*) during the Tang dynasty (around 618-907 AD). The Chinese selectively bred these carp to enhance specific traits, leading to the development of various goldfish varieties that we know today.

The allure of goldfish lies not only in their vibrant colors, which can range from brilliant reds, oranges, and yellows to striking whites and sleek blacks but also in their diverse body shapes. Over centuries of dedicated breeding, enthusiasts and fish keepers have created an astonishing array of goldfish types, including the elegant and elongated Comet, the round and robust Fantail, the exotic and delicate Oranda with its characteristic head growth (wen), and the sleek and graceful Common goldfish, to name just a few.

As pets, goldfish are relatively low-maintenance and are often kept in aquariums. They can live for several years with proper care, and some varieties can grow quite large. Providing a suitable environment, balanced diet, and regular water maintenance are essential for their well-being.

History

Goldfish have a rich history that traces back over a thousand years. They were originally domesticated in ancient China, where they were bred from wild carp. The exact time and location of their domestication are uncertain, but it is believed to have occurred during the Tang Dynasty (618-907 AD). Early Chinese breeders noticed occasional color mutations in carp populations, leading to the development of goldfish with distinct colors and patterns. These colorful variations soon became highly valued and were selectively bred to enhance their appearance.

Characteristics

Goldfish exhibit a variety of colors, including gold, orange, red, white, black, and combinations thereof. They are characterized by their elongated bodies, double caudal (tail) fin, and prominent dorsal (top) fin. Some goldfish breeds have distinctive physical traits, such as bubble eyes, telescope eyes, or fan-shaped tails, which further enhance their visual appeal.

Varieties and Breeds

Over the centuries, numerous goldfish varieties and breeds have been developed through selective breeding. Some popular ones include the Common Goldfish, Comet Goldfish, Shubunkin, Fantail Goldfish, Oranda, Ryukin, and Black Moor, among others. Each variety showcases unique features, colors, and patterns.

Care Requirements

Goldfish are generally considered hardy and easy to care for, making them an ideal choice for beginner fish keepers. However, providing proper care is crucial for their well-being. They require a spacious aquarium or pond with good filtration, as they produce a significant amount of waste. The water temperature should be kept cool, ideally between 65°F to 75°F (18°C to 24°C), depending on the specific variety. Regular water changes and monitoring water quality are essential to maintain a healthy environment for these fish.

Feeding

Goldfish are omnivorous and will eat a variety of foods, including commercial flakes, pellets, and live/frozen foods like brine shrimp, daphnia, and bloodworms. Overfeeding should be avoided as it can lead to health issues, such as swim bladder problems and obesity.

Cultural Significance

Goldfish hold symbolic significance in various cultures. In China, they are seen as a symbol of wealth, prosperity, and good luck. The Japanese appreciate goldfish for their beauty and

elegance, often featuring them in art and during traditional festivals. In Western cultures, goldfish are cherished pets and a common feature in garden ponds and home aquariums.

Lifespan

With proper care, goldfish can live for several years, and some may even reach ages of 10 to 20 years or more. However, their potential lifespan is often limited by suboptimal living conditions or inadequate care.

Social Behavior

Goldfish are generally social and can be kept with other peaceful fish species. However, they can be competitive during feeding, so it's essential to ensure all fish receive adequate food.

Health Concerns

Goldfish are susceptible to various health issues, including swim bladder problems, fungal and bacterial infections, and parasites. Regular observation, proper nutrition, and maintaining good water quality can help prevent many health problems.

Varieties of Goldfish

Common Goldfish

Common goldfish, scientifically known as *Carassius auratus*, are one of the most popular and recognizable types of pet fish worldwide. They belong to the family Cyprinidae and are descendants of the Prussian carp, native to East Asia. Goldfish have been domesticated and selectively bred for various colors, patterns, and body shapes over the centuries, resulting in a wide variety of fancy goldfish breeds.

This is the most basic and oldest variety, often seen as the classic goldfish. It has a long body and single-tail fin.

Comet Goldfish

Comet goldfish (*Carassius auratus* var. comet) are a specific variety of goldfish known for their long, flowing tails and streamlined bodies. They are a type of single-tail goldfish and are closely related to the common goldfish. Comets are one of the hardier goldfish breeds and are well-suited for both indoor aquariums and outdoor ponds.

Similar to the Common Goldfish but with a more elongated and streamlined body. It has a single-tail fin and may display a longer tail.

Fantail Goldfish

Fantail goldfish (*Carassius auratus* var. fantail) are a distinct and popular variety of fancy goldfish known for their attractive appearance and graceful swimming style. They are characterized by their unique double-tail fins, which are split into two lobes, and their round, egg-shaped body. Fantail goldfish have been bred for their ornamental qualities and are commonly kept as pets in aquariums.

Known for their split or double tail, Fantail Goldfish have a rounder body shape and are available in various colors.

Oranda

Oranda goldfish (*Carassius auratus* var. *oranda*) are a captivating and well-loved variety of fancy goldfish. They are prized for their distinct head growth called a "wen," which is a fleshy outgrowth covering the top of their head and sometimes extending over their gills. Orandas are popular among fish enthusiasts due to their charming appearance and peaceful temperament. Like other fancy goldfish, they have been selectively bred for their ornamental qualities.

Recognized by their prominent, bumpy head growth called a "wen," Orandas have a dorsal fin and a split or double tail.

Ryukin

Ryukin goldfish (*Carassius auratus* var. *ryukin*) are a fascinating and attractive variety of fancy goldfish with a distinctive body shape and unique features. They are highly sought after by fish enthusiasts for their elegant appearance and graceful swimming style. Ryukins, like other fancy goldfish, have been selectively bred for their ornamental qualities and are popular choices for aquariums and ponds.

This breed has a hump on the back of its head and a fan-shaped tail.

Telescope Goldfish

Telescope goldfish (*Carassius auratus* var. *telescopicus*) are a captivating and distinctive variety of fancy goldfish known for their protruding eyes, which give them their name. These fish have been selectively bred for their unique appearance and are highly sought after by fish keepers and enthusiasts worldwide. Telescope goldfish are prized for their charming personality and ornamental qualities.

Named for their protruding eyes that resemble a telescope, this variety is available in various colors and tail shapes.

Black Moor

Blackmoor goldfish (*Carassius auratus* var. *black*) are a stunning and captivating variety of fancy goldfish known for their distinctive deep-black coloration and rounded body shape. They are a sought-after breed among fish enthusiasts due to their elegant appearance and peaceful temperament. Blackmoor goldfish have been selectively bred for their ornamental qualities and are popular choices for aquariums and outdoor ponds.

This variety has a velvety black coloration and protruding eyes.

Requirements for Goldfish breeding

Aquarium Size -: Provide a spacious aquarium with enough room for the goldfish to swim freely and lay eggs. At least 20 gallons per pair is recommended.

Water Quality -: Maintain excellent water quality by regularly testing and monitoring parameters like ammonia, nitrite, and nitrate levels. Perform regular water changes to keep the environment clean and stable.

Polluted Water

Pure Water

Water Temperature -: Keep the water temperature between 68-74°F (20-23°C) as this is the ideal range for goldfish breeding.

Measure the Temperature from hand

Filtration -: Use a good filtration system to remove debris and maintain water clarity. Goldfish produce a lot of waste, and a strong filter will help keep the tank clean.

Substrate and Decorations -: Choose a soft substrate to protect the eggs and provide hiding places. Live or artificial plants, spawning mops, or mesh nets can serve as breeding sites for the eggs.

Proper Diet -: Feed a balanced and nutritious diet to your goldfish to ensure they are healthy and ready for breeding. Live or frozen foods can be offered occasionally.

Select Healthy Fish -: Ensure that the parent fish are healthy and free from diseases or deformities before breeding.

Separation -: If you have multiple goldfish, separate the breeding pair into a separate breeding tank to prevent other fish from eating the eggs or disturbing the process.

Water Aeration -: Provide adequate oxygenation through aeration to support the developing fry.

Brood stock development

Brood-stock development plays a major role in goldfish breeding as it directly affects fry success and quality. This process involves the selection and preparation of breeding pairs, known as offspring, to achieve the best genetic characteristics and reproductive potential.

First, breeders carefully select offspring with desirable physical and genetic characteristics. These traits may include color patterns, body shape, and fin structure. Selecting healthy individuals with minimal genetic defects is critical to maintaining the overall health of the goldfish population.

Second, proper brood preparation is essential to ensure successful breeding. This includes providing a balanced and nutritious diet that promotes optimal health and reproductive readiness. A well-balanced diet can include live or frozen foods as well as specific supplements.

Third, maintaining optimal environmental conditions is critical for the development of offspring. Water parameters such as temperature, pH and water quality should be carefully monitored and kept within appropriate ranges. Providing a stress-free and comfortable environment increases the chances of a successful breeding.

Monitoring the offspring's reproductive readiness is also a key part of the developmental process. Observing behavioral cues and physical changes can indicate when a goldfish is ready to breed. Once the chicks are ready, they can be introduced into a specially prepared breeding tank to lay eggs and fertilize them.

Goldfish Breeding

Characteristics of Prospective Goldfish Parents

- Fish in good health, without defects or injuries.
- Parent age between 0.5-1 years.
- The parent scales are large and evenly distributed.
- The condition of the fish scales has no wounds or defects.
- Proportional body size and shape.
- Body texture is not too hard or soft.
- Relatively tall body size.
- The shape of the stomach is flat and wide.
- The tail is normal and thick, with a relatively wide tail base.
- The distance between the base of the tail and the anal opening is relatively close.
- Small head size with a sharp muzzle.

Female Goldfish	Male Goldfish
Minimum 1.5 years old	Minimum 6 months old
Minimum body weight of 1.5 kg	Minimum body weight of 0.5 kg
The texture of the abdomen is soft and swells to the back	When the stomach is pressed, sperm comes out
The urogenital opening is reddish	Agile movement
The body is thicker than the male sires.	The genital opening is not prominent.

Goldfish breeding Steps

Step 01: Tank Preparation

Set up a separate breeding tank with clean, DE chlorinated water. The tank should be adequately sized, around 20-30 gallons, with good filtration.

Add live or artificial plants and spawning mops for the eggs to attach to and for hiding spots.

Prepare the breeding tank

Step 02: Select Healthy Adults

Choose mature and healthy adult goldfish. You'll need a male and a female for breeding.

Make sure they are in good condition and free from diseases.

Selected Female parents

Selected brood-stock

Step 03: Conditioning

Feed the adult goldfish a varied diet rich in protein for a few weeks before breeding. This helps them become more fertile.

Step 04: Temperature and Lighting

Maintain the breeding tank temperature between 68-74°F (20-24°C). A gradual temperature increase might trigger breeding behavior.

Use subdued lighting, as bright light can stress the fish.

Step 05: Introducing the Goldfish

Place the male and female goldfish into the breeding tank. Monitor their behavior closely.

The male might start chasing the female, nudging her, and showing signs of courtship.

Step 06: Egg-Laying

The female will lay eggs, usually adhesive, on the plants or spawning mops. The male will fertilize them by releasing milt over the eggs.

Spawning mops

layer of nets

Step 07: Removing Adults

Once the eggs are laid and fertilized, remove the adult goldfish from the breeding tank. They might eat the eggs if left together.

Step 08: Incubation

The eggs will hatch in around 3-5 days, depending on the water temperature. Keep an eye on the eggs' development. Add methylene blue to protect the eggs from parasites and pathogens.

Methylene blue added tanks

Step 09: Feeding Fry

Once hatched, the fry will have a yolk sac that provides initial nutrition. As it's absorbed, start feeding them very tiny foods like infusoria or liquid fry food.

Gradually transition to larger fry foods as they grow.

Step 10: Water Quality

Maintain excellent water quality by regular partial water changes. Fry are sensitive to poor water conditions.

Unhealthy water

Water condition improving

Step 11: Separation

As the fry grow, you might need to separate them by size to prevent larger ones from bullying or eating smaller ones.

Step 12: Growing Fry

Continue feeding and caring for the fry as they develop. You can gradually introduce larger foods like brine shrimp and crushed flakes.

Artemia live feed

Prima 00

Artemia can

Spawning habits

During the breeding season, prior to mating, goldfish engage in a sequence of courtship rituals that involve various actions and displays intended to entice a prospective mate. Male goldfish usually engage in these behaviors because they are actively seeking female goldfish to mate with.

Female goldfish often hunt around the tank or pond during the courtship ritual in an attempt to lure the male goldfish to a location that will facilitate successful mating.

One of the most interesting parts of their courtship behavior is how males use their fins to communicate with female goldfish. Males display their colors and fins as they imitate a dance to impress their female counterparts, ready to mate and prove their suitability as a mate.

During mating season, males develop small white or pink bumps on their fins, called breeding tubercles. These tubercles serve as a visual cue for females, letting them know that the male is ready for mating and well matched. It is common for a male goldfish to court multiple females at the same time, but it is rare.

Additionally, pheromone use is a fundamental part of goldfish courtship behavior. The pheromones that male goldfish emit into the water can signal to females that they are ready for a romantic relationship. Because males are able to attract females without direct physical contact, this chemical communication is crucial in courtship.

In general, goldfish courtship behavior is a unique and complex process involving various behavioral and visual cues. By putting on courtship displays to entice and impress potential female mates, males increase their chances of successfully reproducing.

The spawning process begins after the male adult goldfish has successfully attracted the female goldfish. Spawning usually occurs in the spring, when the days are longer and water temperatures are rising.

Male goldfish tend to grow more aggressive and territorial during this time, building nests out of plants or other materials to attract females.

When a female goldfish is ready to spawn, she releases her eggs into the water. The male then releases the milt to fertilize the eggs by releasing the milt into the water. Many male adult fish may compete with one female for the opportunity to mate during this fertilization phase, which usually occurs close to the nest.

Goldfish Breeding Behaviors

Hatching

Identifying a Goldfish Egg

Goldfish eggs look like a variety of fish and invertebrates. An easy rule of thumb to determine what the tank's egg stock is is to find out the different types of aquarium life in your tank. If you have a goldfish only tank, chances are it is only goldfish eggs. If you have snails or other suitable tankmates, you should take note of what their eggs look like.

Goldfish eggs appear as white to yellow or orange bubbles. They are small fine dots that usually stick to the substrate and leave the inside of the tank. Goldfish eggs are incredibly sticky and can be difficult to remove. Goldfish eggs will also be abundant as the female can lay over 300 eggs depending on her age, size and health.

Because the eggs are difficult to remove, you may want to place a brood mop or a variety of live plants to trap the goldfish eggs. The more hidden they are, the less likely parents are to find and eat them.

Hatching

- Place eggs attached to a spawning mop, plant, or decoration in a hatchery/incubation tank with a filter, heater, and aeration system.
- Keep eggs at a warm constant temperature of 21°C to 24°C. Be sure to use a heater to keep the temperature constant. This encourages egg hatching in 3 to 5 days.

- Eggs should be aerated with an air stone, bubbler or spray bar. Eggs require plenty of oxygenated water to hatch.
- Infertile eggs will be pure white, while fertile eggs will appear transparent. This is seen after a day or two.
- After five days, the young will hatch and appear as small dots around the water in clusters.

Hatching Tanks

Goldfish Fryes

Larval rearing and maintaining

Setup of the Habitat and Water Quality

Larvae may need particular environmental parameters, such as temperature, pH, salinity, and oxygen levels, depending on the species.

Maintain ideal water quality by routine inspection and alterations. Common procedures include filtration, aeration, and water exchange.

Improving Water Quality

Feeding

Give larvae the proper nutrients. Depending on the species, they may have very different dietary needs.

Provide suitable sources of living or artificial food. Algae, zooplankton, Artemia (brine shrimp), and prepared larval meals are popular choices.

Artemia (Live feed)

Prima 00

Egg mixture

Building a tank

Create the raising tanks as closely as feasible to the larvae's natural environment.

Take into account elements like substrate, hiding spots, tank size, and water flow patterns.

Proper Tank sizes

Care and handling

Larvae should be handled gently to prevent stress and damage. Utilize the right tools and approaches when transferring them.

Goldfish Fry size

Conclusion

Goldfish breeding is a multifaceted endeavor involving various factors that contribute to the successful propagation of these attractive aquatic creatures. By paying careful attention to water quality, temperature regulation, tank dimensions and genetic compatibility, breeders can optimize the conditions necessary for a successful breeding environment. Patience, commitment and a broad understanding of the complexities involved are critical to ensuring the health and vitality of mother fish and their young.

When starting this journey it is essential to consider the natural behavior of goldfish and their breeding patterns. Adequate research and preparation will give breeders the knowledge to recognize the signs of calving readiness and facilitate the process appropriately. Careful selection of suitable mates based on physical attributes and genetic traits increases the likelihood of producing healthy and visually attractive offspring.

When hatching begins, close monitoring is essential so that eggs can be removed in time to protect against potential cannibalism or contamination. Providing a safe and nurturing environment for developing eggs and chicks that includes proper aeration and water movement will greatly affect their survival.

Furthermore, the later stages of chick care require diligent attention, focusing on their nutrition, growth and social dynamics. Live or specialized fry food, regular monitoring of water parameters and partial water changes will help their healthy development. Segregation of offspring based on size and growth rates may be necessary to prevent size-based competition and ensure equitable access to resources.

In conclusion, goldfish breeding is a rewarding but complex pursuit that requires a comprehensive understanding of aquatic biology, behavior and environmental factors. Through careful planning, monitoring and care, breeders can participate in the exciting process of nurturing new life while contributing to the diversity and vitality of the goldfish community.

Author : R.M.P.P. Bandula

Undergraduate

Bachelor of Bio systems Technology

In Agricultural Technology

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